

A survey on IoT in the era Artificial Intelligence - Exploring the impact of AI on IoT

Ba20669317 Eleni Stavari

1. ABSTRACT

The internet is constantly evolving. From the internet of computers (IoC) to the Internet of things (IoT). AI is the study of putting intelligence in machines so that they can perform jobs that previously needed the human mind. Artificial intelligence systems are quickly evolving in terms of application, adaptation capabilities and processing time. IoC is in existence since 1991 and it has grown in size so much that now is considered IoT. That is due to the introduction of pocket phones and connected gadgets. The internet of gadgets began and eventually it expanded as mobile phones, PCS, laptops and tablets became more affordable and available to the general public. (1). IoT is a network of various devices connected over the internet that collect and exchange data with each other. These IoT devices generate a lot of data that needs to be collected and mined for actionable results through the use of AI to manage massive data flows and storage in the IoT network(2). But what impact has AI in our everyday life? How artificial intelligence in the internet of things benefit us and what are the dangers that come with it? What are the future outlook? These are the questions that are going to be answered in this paper.

2. INTRODUCTION

AI was developed to create computer programs capable of learning. Early scientists, including Alan Mathison Turing, John von Neuman and Norbert Wiener aimed to create programs capable of self-copying, learning and controlling their environment. Their goal was to model the human brain, mimic human learning and stimulate biological evolution (3).

In 1999, British technology pioneer Kevin Ashton coined the phrase "internet of things" to refer to a system that connects real things to the Internet using sensors. He invented the term to highlight the potential of connecting RFID tags in corporate supply chain to the Internet for automated tracking and inventory management. The IoT refers to scenarios where objects, devices, sensors and everyday items have access to the Internet and computational power (4).

IoT involves embedding short-range transceivers in various gadgets and ordinary objects allowing for a new communication methods between people, things and oneself. As a result the internet of things offers a new level to information and communication (5). Connecting devices to the Internet allows you to access distant sensor data and manipulate the real world from a distance (6). The IoT has evolved into wide range of creative integrated solutions for specific applications via three development paths: authentication, communication and computation (7) The set of Artificial Intelligence, Machine learning and large- scale data are having an ever increasing impact on our future lives and businesses (8)

Artificial Intelligence can be divided into several branches, among which stand out automatic learning, computer vision, Fuzzy logic, natural language processing , heuristics and intelligent agents(14)

3. APPLICATIONS OF AI IN IOT

3.1 application of AI in education

Computers have been used in teaching for more than 20 years. Computer based training and computer- aided instruction were the first technologies used to teach with computers. In these methods, instruction was not tailored to the learners needs. Instead judgment on how to progress a student through the subject were scripted such as “ if question 21 is answered correct then go to 54 otherwise go to 32”. The learners talents were not considered. This lead to a research on intelligent tutoring systems (ITSs). ITSs provide substantial flexibility in material presentation and greater ability to respond to individual student requirements. These system acquire “intelligence” by reflecting educational judgments and learners information. Changing the systems interactions with the student increases its adaptability. Intelligent tutoring methods improve student performance and motivation(9).

3.2 applications of ai in the medical field

It has been discovered that AI has major applications in the medical field. Nowadays AI is being used in the medical field to preserve medical records in digital forms and conduct patient check ups utilizing smart technology. It offers solutions particularly in the form of targeted treatments, medications that are unique in composition and personalized therapies. AI is revolutionary technology that assists surgeons with medicine, therapy and surgery. The primary

application of this is to improve decision making in complex scenarios.. It can also assist track, detect , analyze and control infections in hospitals. This technology creates and optimizes online patient appointment platforms. (10)

3.3 application of AI in environmental disciplines

In the last decade environmental discipline has seen an increase in interest in leveraging the possibilities in AI. The amount of electricity consumed and the time necessary to train an AI model can have a significant impact on the carbon emissions produced, increasing the issues posed by climate change. Efforts are presently underway to create AI that is environmental friendly, uses less energy and has minimal carbon footprint. Choosing the right AI model design can save energy consumption by over 90% (11)

3.4 Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Transport

The application of AI in transportation aims to address the difficulties of rising travel demand, CO2 emissions , safety concerns and environmental degradation. In the light of the availability of a great amount of quantitative and qualitative data and AI in current digital age, addressing these challenges in a more efficient and effective method has become more feasible.

Transportation issues arise when the system and user behavior are too difficult to model and forecast. As a result, AI is regarded as a suitable solution. These issues stem from the continual increase in rural and urban traffic caused by growing populations, especially in emerging countries.(12)

3.4 Other applications

1. Gaming Industry

Chess is one of the most well-known applications of AI in game business. Although not as sophisticated as humans machines use brute force algorithms and scan 100's of spots every second to identify the next move. AI utilized in Microsoft Xbox 360's Kinect to detect body motion. However, it is still in the early stages and requires significant development before it can have more practical applications.

2. Heavy Industries

AI robots are increasingly used in high risk industries, replacing human workers. Robots are more efficient than people due to their lack of fatigue.

3. Weather Forecasting

Neural networks are increasingly being utilized to forecast meteorological conditions. The neural networks uses past data to analyze patterns and predict future weather conditions. Expert systems are educated to have complete knowledge in specific areas of interest. They are designed to address difficulties in certain areas. These systems use statistical analysis and data mining to solve problems by answering yes-no questions logically. (13)

4. RULES OF AI

1. AI must be designed to help humans. AI should enhance human talents and enrich human lives not replace or diminish them.

2. AI must be transparent. People should understand how AI systems work and make decisions. There should be explicit communication about AI's capabilities and limitations.

3. AI must balance effectiveness and human dignity. It must uphold cultural values while promoting diversity. A wider, deeper, and more diverse

Commitment to the populace is essential, as technology should not determine future ideals and virtues.

4. AI must be developed to provide intelligent privacy. Protecting personal information requires sophisticated strategies to build trust.

5. AI should have algorithmic duty to prevent unforeseen consequences. AI technology must be designed to account for both expected and unexpected scenarios.

6. To avoid prejudice, AI must conduct adequate and representative study to prevent discrimination from erroneous heuristics.

Satya Nadella suggests that people prioritize and cultivate certain attributes to coexist with AIs, including:

1. Empathy is essential for building relationships and understanding others' feelings and thoughts, which machines cannot imitate.
2. Education is essential for embracing and managing uncharted innovations. Investing in education is crucial for gaining the knowledge and skills required to deploy new technologies and tackle time-consuming problems.
3. Machines will enhance creativity, a highly valued human trait.
4. Accepting a machine-generated diagnostic or legal determination, but recognizing that a human is ultimately accountable for making the final choice. (45)

5. BENEFITS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The rapid improvements in machine learning and AI along with easily available processing capacity to execute these algorithms on the smallest of devices, lead to new discoveries in scientific discovery and commercial applications across many fields and sectors.(15)

Industrial processes and equipment assisted by AI systems significantly improve human's abilities to provide digital assistance and make decisions in critical and very complicated scenarios.(16)As with past technological revolutions (e.g. industrial,digital) the use of AI in business has the potential to dramatically transform the marketplace and have a significant impact on economies and jobs(17). Adoption of AI applications will benefit enterprises, value chains, society and the economy. It can enhance manufacturing efficiency, minimize maintenance costs, improve energy efficiency optimize raw material consumption and eliminate waste. AI can improve product personalization, improve customer service and drive innovation in new categories, business models and sectors. It provide workforce benefits such as workplace safety. And it can be cheaper than human activity(19).

Many public sector organization could benefit from public authorities using AI. Some examples are drone navigation, medical treatment , prioritizing, bail hearings, citizen inquiry, public facility design, fraud detection, benefit distribution(20). It is important to understand better the use of AI. When AI systems are made available to general public they can cause unexpected

shifts in behavior (22)The government services can be improved by AI(21)as it can improve government programs, regulations and operations(23)

Also we are aware of the tremendous potential for AI to provide substantial advantages to underserved communities, improving equal access to public services such as health, education, social assistance or public transit(24).AI integration in health care promises increased diagnostic accuracy, informed decision making and better treatment planning, lowering potential medical errors and increasing patients outcomes(25). It will also provide more individualized treatment regimens and more efficient resource allocation(26) In education AI will create individualized learning experiences. Large class numbers and inadequate resources might make it challenging for traditional classrooms to meet student's different learning requirements.AI systems may monitor student performance in real time, alter learning materials and offer personalized recommendations for development(27). It can also be beneficial for scientific research(28)

6. CHALLENGES AND ETHICAL CONCERNS

Artificial intelligence is becoming seamlessly integrated into our everyday lives this has been helpful in many sectors but is it ideal? What are the dangers of a technology like this and the role that now plays in our lives.

The history of IoT is one of enormous success as evidenced by position it now occupies in the global technology ecosystem in which an increasing majority of people live. To some extent IoT has become so prevalent that it is no longer seen as distinct from mainstream technology since devices have become an integral part of our everyday life. So we will see a global intelligence of the devices and outline a wider link between humans and machines (29)

It is obvious that the future evolution of the service sector will be dependent on the proper exploitation of the opportunities provided by AI and other Industry 4.0. technologies. The problem we confront is to capitalize on the potential provided by these technologies, but also for the end consumers who will appreciate them and be ready to use them(30)

The psychological impacts of AI ethics includes challenges such as protecting against undue manipulation, agreeing to data gathering and recognizing when one is interacting with non human . The societal impact includes issues about justice and fairness. AI ethics political significance extends to democratic processes , rights and the economy (32).The next generation of AI will have greater impact on our lives through regular interactions and making critical decisions on our behalf, frequently in highly personalized circumstances. This presents tremendous hurdles(31). It has the potential to increase inequality by concentrating money,

resources and decision making power in the hands of a select few countries , companies or individuals. Also AI automates regular tasks that were previously performed by humans and the cost of hiring human resources is reduced(35). Researchers say that there is a big concern related to ai and that the disadvantages could be publicly and exhaustively.(36). The threat of general purpose generative AI is not the technology itself. The concern is that humans particularly the leaders of the AI sector think that it is the type of "intelligence" that can be generatively stored by AIs.(46)

Given its multidimensional nature artificial intelligence automatically touches on a wide range of legal subjects including legal theory, human rights , contract law, tort law , criminal law, tax law and procedural law. In reality there is barely any sector of law that is unaffected by artificial intelligence.(33). While AI is only now beginning to gain traction in terms of its usage by attorneys legal scholars have been interested in ai for a long time its dates back to 1991(34)

One of the biggest consents for the use of ai in the iot is the ecological impact that it has. The energy consumption associated with AI technologies particularly deep learning models is significant. Training large scale AI models such as GPT-3 necessitates enormous processing power which consumes a huge amount of energy(37). For example training GPT-3 consumed 1,287MWh of electricity , which is equal to the annual energy usage of more than 120 US houses. This translates into significant carbon emissions , which contribute to the overall carbon footprint of AI systems.(38). Data centers consume approximately 200 terawatt hours(TWh) per year . This amount exceeds national energy consumption energy in some countries such as Iran, but only accounts for half of global transportation electricity and 1% of global power demand. Data centers account for 0.3% of global carbon emissions while the ecosystem including personal digital devices , mobile networks and televisions accounts for over 2%(39)

7. FUTURE OUTLOOK

Today, technology and data assists and make decisions in our daily lives. As a results , every industry must adapt to the changing times by embracing AI in order to become sustainable in the future.(40). The integration of AI into various aspects of human life is underway and the complex ethical concerns raised by the technology's design , deployment and use serve as a reminder that it is time to revisit what future developers and designers are learning about AI. It is critical to be trained to reflect on the ways in which may AI may touch people's lives and accept their duties to enhance its benefits while limiting the downsides(41) .They need to be schooled

in more nuanced skills because those will most likely be the domain where humans will continue to surpass AI.(42). The AI4Eq movement encourages collaboration among academics, AI developers, civil society and government policymakers to create a technological transformation that benefits society, reduces inequality and ensures no one falls behind (43). AI systems require ethical guidelines in addition to their primary functions(44). Lastly, we have to integrate sustainability in AI is crucial because the environmental impact that it has . We need to boost environmental protection, regulatory compliance and ethical responsibility.

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